

Government as a Platform

Orchestrating stakeholders in crisis situations through digital platforms

Project Report (2023 – 2026)

Executive Summary

The Ukrainian refugee crisis showed how difficult the orchestration of crisis response can become during a large-scale emergency. Since 2022, around 130,000 Ukrainian refugees have been admitted to Switzerland within a short period of time¹. Cantonal offices, municipalities, NGOs, volunteers, and private actors all contributed to the response, but the crisis highlighted a central challenge: existing administrative systems were not designed to orchestrate diverse stakeholders under time pressure, fragmentation, and uncertainty.

This report concludes a three-year research initiative (2023–2026) funded by the Digitalization Initiative of the Zurich Higher Education Institutions (DIZH). The project investigated how the Government as a Platform (GaaP) approach can improve the orchestration of diverse stakeholders during crises, using the Ukrainian refugee crisis in the Canton of Zurich as the primary case study.

The unprecedented speed and scale of the Ukrainian refugee crisis strained traditional administrative systems. Drawing on our in-depth case study, we identified the following **bottlenecks in digital crisis response**:

- **Manual and Unscalable Processes:** Administrative workflows were often manual, leading to system failure under high demand.
- **Information Silos:** Data exchange between cantonal offices, municipalities, and NGOs was frequently unsystematic, relying on emails and Excel sheets rather than integrated IT systems.
- **Fragmentation of Responsibility:** Strong Swiss federalism, while allowing for local flexibility, created "broken connections" where refugees and hosts struggled to navigate unclear organizational boundaries.

To address these challenges, we proposed and prototyped a **Government as a Platform framework** adapted to the Swiss context. GaaP transforms the public sector into an open platform that enables the orchestration of government agencies, private actors, NGOs, and citizens through a shared digital core, applications, and an ecosystem of complementors contributing services and innovation during crises.

The following work packages represent the main pillars of the project to achieve that vision:

Platform core:

- **"Crizzy" Platform Prototype:** A central digital infrastructure serving as a "single point of entry" for refugees and organizations.
- **eID for refugees:** A decentralized eID solution that empowers refugees to manage their own identity data securely, reducing redundant paperwork for authorities.

Applications:

- **Data-driven AI solutions in crisis:** tools for better informing during the crisis. RefuGPT is a LLM-based chatbot that integrates official government data with community insights. R2G (Refugees to Government) is a data-driven intelligence tool to provide policymakers with bottom-up insights into refugee needs.
- **Hackathon for crisis apps:** event to test the Government as a Platform concept within the Swiss context by bringing together multiple stakeholders—including developers, NGOs, and public administrators—to co-create digital solutions for real-life crisis challenges.

Ecosystem:

- **Estonian Case Study:** a comparative analysis to evaluate the world-leading Estonian GaaP model and identify how a mature digital state architecture effectively orchestrated refugee support, providing a benchmark for refining Switzerland's transition from manual "silos" to an integrated digital ecosystem.

¹ <https://www.blick.ch/politik/das-musst-du-jetzt-zum-schutzstatus-wissen-so-viele-ukrainer-wie-nie-in-der-schweiz-id21958856.html>

- **Governance-by-Action:** a proposed mode of governance where coordination emerges through action rather than formal authority: roles overlap, decisions are made locally, and ownership is shared collectively.

Our findings demonstrate that GaaP can bridge the gap between the strengths of decentralized federal governance and the need for coordinated crisis response. By establishing common boundary resources (tools and rules), the government can leverage the agility of the private sector and civil society without compromising safety or legitimacy. This project provides a roadmap for the Canton of Zurich—and potentially the whole of Switzerland—to move toward a more resilient, human-centric, and digitally connected public sector.

Zusammenfassung

Die ukrainische Flüchtlingskrise hat gezeigt, wie schwierig die Koordination einer Krisenreaktion bei einem Grossschadensereignis werden kann. Seit 2022 wurden in kurzer Zeit rund 130'000 ukrainische Geflüchtete in der Schweiz aufgenommen². Kantonsämter, Gemeinden, NGOs, Freiwillige und private Akteure haben alle zur Reaktion beigetragen, doch die Krise hat eine zentrale Herausforderung deutlich gemacht: Bestehende Verwaltungssysteme sind nicht darauf ausgelegt, diverse Akteure unter Zeitdruck, Fragmentierung und Unsicherheit zu koordinieren.

Dieser Bericht schliesst eine dreijährige Forschungsinitiative (2023–2026) ab, die von der Digitalisierungsinitiative der Zürcher Hochschulen (DIZH) gefördert wurde. Das Projekt untersuchte, wie der «Government as a Platform»-Ansatz (GaaP) die Koordination verschiedener Akteure in Krisen verbessern kann, wobei die ukrainische Flüchtlingskrise im Kanton Zürich als zentrales Fallbeispiel diente.

Die beispiellose Geschwindigkeit und das Ausmass der ukrainischen Flüchtlingskrise haben traditionelle Verwaltungssysteme an ihre Grenzen gebracht. Auf der Grundlage unserer vertieften Fallstudie haben wir folgende Engpässe in der digitalen Krisenreaktion identifiziert:

- **Manuelle und nicht skalierbare Prozesse:** Verwaltungsabläufe waren häufig manuell gestaltet, was bei hoher Nachfrage zu Systemausfällen führte.
- **Informationssilos:** Der Datenaustausch zwischen Kantonsämtern, Gemeinden und NGOs erfolgte oft unsystematisch und stützte sich auf E-Mails und Excel-Tabellen anstatt auf integrierte IT-Systeme.
- **Fragmentierung der Verantwortung:** Der ausgeprägte Schweizer Föderalismus ermöglichte zwar lokale Flexibilität, schuf aber auch «unterbrochene Verbindungen», bei denen Geflüchtete und Gastgebende Mühe hatten, sich in unklaren Organisationsstrukturen zurechtzufinden.

Um diesen Herausforderungen zu begegnen, haben wir ein auf den Schweizer Kontext zugeschnittenes **Government-as-a-Platform-Framework** vorgeschlagen und prototypisch umgesetzt. GaaP transformiert den öffentlichen Sektor in eine offene Plattform, die die Koordination von Behörden, privaten Akteuren, NGOs und Bürgerinnen und Bürgern ermöglicht – gestützt auf einen gemeinsamen digitalen Plattformkern, Anwendungen und ein Ökosystem von Komplementoren, die im Krisenfall Lösungen und Innovationen beisteuern.

Die folgenden Arbeitspakete bilden die Hauptpfeiler des Projekts zur Verwirklichung dieser Vision:

Plattformkern:

- **«Crizzy»-Plattformprototyp:** Eine zentrale digitale Plattform als «Single Point of Entry» für Geflüchtete und Organisationen.
- **eID für Geflüchtete:** Eine dezentralisierte eID-Lösung, die Geflüchteten ermöglicht, ihre Identitätsdaten selbstbestimmt und sicher zu verwalten, und damit den Verwaltungsaufwand für Behörden reduziert.

Applikationen:

- **KI-Lösungen in der Krise:** Werkzeuge zur besseren Information während der Krise. RefuGPT ist ein LLM-basierter Chatbot, der offizielle Behördendaten mit Community-Wissen verbindet. R2G (Refugees to Government) ist ein datengestütztes Informationswerkzeug, das politisch Verantwortlichen Bottom-up-Einblicke in die Bedürfnisse Geflüchteter liefert.
- **Hackathon für Krisen-Apps:** Eine Veranstaltung zur Erprobung des GaaP-Konzepts im Schweizer Kontext, bei der verschiedene Akteure – darunter Entwicklerinnen und Entwickler, NGOs und

² <https://www.blick.ch/politik/das-musst-du-jetzt-zum-schutzstatus-wissen-so-viele-ukrainer-wie-nie-in-der-schweiz-id21958856.html>

Verwaltungsvertreterinnen und -vertreter – gemeinsam digitale Lösungen für reale Krisenszenarien erarbeiteten.

Ökosystem:

- **Fallstudie «GaaP in Estland»:** Eine vergleichende Analyse des weltweit führenden estnischen GaaP-Modells, um zu ermitteln, wie eine ausgereifte digitale Staatsarchitektur die Flüchtlingsunterstützung wirksam koordinierte – als Referenzpunkt für die Weiterentwicklung der Schweiz vom manuellen «Silosystem» hin zu einem integrierten digitalen Ökosystem.
- **Governance-by-Action:** Ein vorgeschlagener Governance-Modus, bei dem Koordination durch Handeln entsteht statt durch formale Autorität: Rollen überschneiden sich, Entscheidungen werden lokal getroffen, und Verantwortung wird kollektiv geteilt.

Unsere Ergebnisse zeigen, dass GaaP die Lücke zwischen den Stärken dezentraler Bundesstaatlichkeit und dem Bedürfnis nach koordinierter Krisenreaktion schliessen kann. Durch die Schaffung gemeinsamer sog. Boundary Resources (digitale Werkzeuge und Regeln), die allen Akteuren offenstehen, kann der Staat die Agilität des Privatsektors und der Zivilgesellschaft nutzen, ohne dabei Sicherheit oder Legitimität zu beeinträchtigen. Dieses Projekt liefert einen Fahrplan für den Kanton Zürich – und potenziell für die gesamte Schweiz – hin zu einem resilienteren, menschenzentrierten und digital vernetzten öffentlichen Sektor.

Content

- MOTIVATION & GOALS..... 7**
- STUDY RESULTS – AT A GLANCE 8**
- PROJECT QUICK FACTS 9**
 - ROADMAP & METHODOLOGY 10
- CASE STUDY: UKRAINIAN REFUGEE CRISIS IN THE CANTON ZURICH.....11**
 - UKRAINIAN REFUGEE CRISIS: BRIEF OVERVIEW 12
 - “REFUGEE JOURNEY”: SUCCESSES & CHALLENGES 13
 - ORCHESTRATION OF THE ACTORS 22
- GOVERNMENT AS A PLATFORM CONCEPT.....23**
 - GOVERNMENT AS A PLATFORM GLOSSARY 23
 - GAAP BEST PRACTICES. ESTONIAN CASE STUDY..... 24
- POTENTIALS OF GAAP FOR CRISIS25**
- PLATFORM PROTOTYPE26**
 - FIRST ITERATION 27
 - SECOND ITERATION 28
- PLATFORM APPLICATIONS30**
 - SSI FOR REFUGEES 30
 - DATA-DRIVEN INTELLIGENCE IN CRISIS 31
 - HACKATHON ON CRISIS APPS (2025, UZH) 32
- PLATFORM GOVERNANCE: FROM PROTOTYPE TO INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY34**
 - LEGAL FINDINGS 34
- WAY FORWARD36**
- LIST OF ACRONYMS.....37**
- ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS38**
- REFERENCES.....39**
- APPENDIX 1. LIST OF INTERVIEWS.....41**
- APPENDIX 2. PROJECT PUBLICATIONS.....42**

Motivation & Goals

Since 2022, almost 6 million Ukrainian refugees have come to Europe, making it the largest migration crisis in Europe since World War II [1]. The influx of Ukrainian refugees was also unprecedented for Switzerland: since the conflict began, Switzerland has admitted approximately 130,000 refugees from Ukraine, almost 20,000 of whom now reside in Zurich, constituting 1,2% of total population [2]. What made the situation critical is the unprecedented speed of migration. This time in one month Switzerland received five times more refugees as usually at one point of time.

In response, multiple actors, including municipalities, cantonal and federal agencies, private housing providers, schools, employers, NGOs, and volunteers, have mobilized to support these refugees. Civic engagement has been notably strong, but the diverse actors have faced various challenges. These include inadequate access to timely information, resource shortages, coordination issues, inefficient administrative processes, and barriers such as language and culture.

To help coordinate actions in crisis situations, the *Government as a Platform (GaaP)* concept offers a promising approach to the public sector's digital transformation, focusing on human-centric innovation. GaaP enables public sectors to function as open platforms, facilitating collaboration among governmental and non-governmental actors to provide more effective public services. Many countries, such as Italy, the UK, Norway, and Estonia, have embraced GaaP to enhance service provision, but its application during crises remains underexplored. Moreover, there is a need for further empirical studies, particularly in federal states like Switzerland, to assess GaaP's impact on public innovation and service delivery.

This report argues that the GaaP approach is well-suited for the canton of Zurich to enhance the orchestration of the diverse actors involved in crisis management and improve overall societal resilience. An analysis of existing digitalization initiatives at both the cantonal [3] and federal [4] levels suggests that the GaaP approach aligns with current strategic priorities. We aim to provide a framework for integrating digital platforms to improve the coordination of efforts during crises and enhance the resilience of Zurich's public sector, with a potential for the whole Switzerland. Our central research questions are the following:

- RQ1: How can the GaaP approach improve orchestration of the various actors involved in a crisis by providing means for better collaboration and coordination?
- RQ2: How can the proposed solution based on the Ukrainian refugee crisis be generalized to further potential crisis and thus strengthen the resilience of society?

This report summarizes the findings of a Rapid-Action-Call (RAC) project³ and the follow-up DIZH Project Call "*Government as a Platform: Orchestrating stakeholders in crisis situations through digital platforms*"⁴. Both projects are funded by the Digitalization Initiative of the Zurich Higher Education Institutions (DIZH) and focus on analyzing the Ukraine refugee crisis and exploring how GaaP could address the challenges faced by different actors. To meet the diverse needs of a crisis, we propose that public administrations assume platform characteristics, transforming into open hubs where various actors can co-create solutions.

Today, more than 4 years after the start of the war, most of the refugees with status S still reside in Switzerland. The situation for public administration is no longer that critical. As the main focus of the project is crisis response, our aim is to learn from the previous experience and build digital resilience of the society.

This report will be valuable to public sector professionals, policymakers, and digital government scholars, providing insights into the experiences of refugees, the challenges of crisis management, and the potential of GaaP to strengthen societal resilience. It covers all activities within project and can be read through or as well as by sections.

³ <https://www.dizh.uzh.ch/en/2022/06/07/government-as-is-a-platform-2/>

⁴ <https://www.dizh.uzh.ch/en/2023/02/06/government-as-a-platform-orchestrating-stakeholders-in-crisis-situations-through-digital-platforms/>

Study Results – at a Glance

Enabling **collaboration between actors of private and public sector** during crisis is one of the key motivations for the current project.

Today, 4 years after the start of the war, most of the refugees with status S still reside in Switzerland. The situation for public administration is no longer that critical. The main focus of the project is to **learn from the previous experience** and **build digital resilience** of the society.

The **silo-structure of the IT systems** does not allow for quick coordination and adaptation to during the crisis. As it was mentioned in one of the interviews with the public administration: “Currently there is no holistic approach for the IT systems in the canton of Zurich”. (Interview PA 4)

“**This is not that much of a technical challenge but organizational**”: although technologically GaaP is a complex and resource-heavy solution but one of the key challenges lies in the legal and organizational aspects.

No end-to-end processes. Due to the strong federal system in Switzerland and well-established principles of subsidiarity, refugee-related processes, which often span across jurisdictions, are difficult to follow. They vary from canton to canton and within canton from municipality to municipality.

“*Not even one office of the canton [. . .] can share personal information with another office of the canton internally*” (Interview PA 1, 49:48). This results in many **data being transferred via emails, excel sheets, phone calls, etc.** Thus, the data exchange between organizations is unsystematic, difficult to trace, slow or error prone.

Existing processes are not scalable. In regular time administrative processes work well, but they are not scalable, and once there are that many people the system fails.

The **lack of a legal obligation** on the part of the public administration to play an active role in developing the “Government as a platform” concept is one of the key barriers to its implementation.

Swiss federalism has a two-sided effect. On one hand, public administration at lower levels (cantonal, municipal) had the freedom to act independently, which helped many actors respond to the crisis early without waiting for instructions 'from above.' On the other hand, refugees found it difficult to navigate an unfamiliar bureaucratic environment, while locals struggled to provide a coordinated response.

GaaP & Federal States. The GaaP approach combines the strength of the decentralized systems while ensuring coordination, interoperability and one-point access.

GaaP as money- and resource-efficient solution. By working in silos and repeatedly building the same things, the public administration effort and resources were duplicated. We propose creating a solution following GaaP principles that would make user-centered public services easier to build and cheaper to run.

Proposed GaaP solution is adapted to Swiss reality. Our solution is based on the case study which identifies strengths of the local administrative system and address the existing challenges with the digital solutions.

Project Quick Facts

Current project started with a *Rapid action call (RAC)* DIZH funding back in 2022 [5]. Its main purpose was the needs identification and the proof of concept that GaaP could serve as a potential solution. The follow-up project got a DIZH funding for the realization of the proposed concept (2023 – 2026).

Figure 1: From Framework to Realization

Research Team (UZH & ZHAW)

The project is carried out by an interdisciplinary team (Figure 2) based in University of Zurich (UZH) and Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW). *Prof. Dr. Liudmila Zavolokina* (UZH, associated researcher) and *Prof. Dr. Gerhard Schwabe* (UZH, professor) bring expertise from information systems discipline and eGovernment research. *Prof. Dr. Gianluca Miscione* (ZHAW) brings expertise to the governance topics within the project. Further, two PhD students, *Kilian Sprenkamp* and *Renjun Tang*, and one researcher, *Zoya Katashinskaya* with the information systems background are part of the team. *Kateryna Shapovalova*, a PhD student in law, is consulting the project. Further, the project occasionally involves university students who write their bachelor or master thesis within its scope.

Practice Partners & Project Community

The project aims for interdisciplinary collaboration between researchers and practice partners. Among our partners are both representatives of public administration and private sector. Those are *State Chancellery (Zurich)*, *Ergon Informatik AG*, *Red Cross Switzerland* and *Campax*.

On top of that we have built a community around our project with whom we consult regularly on the various parts of the project. Among them are both researchers and practitioners. With our partners and community, we organize regular meetings where we share our research insights and gather feedback. From the research perspective people from UZH, ETH, University of Lausanne, Bern, Lyon, ZHAW, TU Munich as well as independent researchers. From the practical side we are in contact with public administration offices (cantonal and city administration, municipalities, egovpartner, etc.), refugee-related organizations (AOZ, Caritas, SFH, ORS, etc.) and IT companies (Procivis, iWeb, TrustRelay, etc.).

For more information on project and our updates you can find on the website: gaap-uzh.gitbook.io/wiki/

Figure 2: Research team.

Roadmap & Methodology

The project mainly combines two approaches: design science research (DSR) [6] and action design research (ADR) [7]. DSR is a widely used research method for designing and evaluating IT artifacts that address classes of real-world problems, such as the one in our project. DSR resembles agile software development methodologies but results in generalized knowledge about the design of IT artifacts. Complementing DSR, ADR embeds the designed IT artifact into the organizational context, ensuring its relevance. Both methodologies are well-established and recognized in the information systems and eGovernment disciplines. The project runs until Q2 of 2026 and includes 4 work packages, as summarized in Figure 3: Project Roadmap.

Figure 3: Project Roadmap

Case Study: Ukrainian Refugee Crisis in the Canton Zurich

As the first step in our project, we conducted a comprehensive case study on the Ukrainian refugee crisis with the goal of understanding the problems and outlining concepts for their possible solutions. Shortly after the crisis and still while the situation was very acute, we have conducted 55 interviews with diverse actors involved in the crisis (Figure 1). All interviews were anonymized so that participants could speak freely. Additionally, an analysis of the existing digital solutions for crisis was performed together with analysis of crisis-related social media and survey with 600 Ukrainian refugees. Based on the interviews and our research we have first reconstructed so-called **refugee journey** – a map of activities that refugees had to go through and involved actors. Overview of the interview you can find in Appendix 1. List of Interviews.

In this report, we present an overview of the key findings of our case study. We have listed the **challenges and success** of various stakeholder groups (public administration, NGOs & businesses, volunteers, refugees) that we have identified during the crisis. Those are organized along three categories: technical, organizational and cultural. Identified challenges are the main motivation for the project and they will be addressed by the proposed GaaP solution. Observed positive experiences and new solutions provide us with an inspiration and will be equally supported by the proposed GaaP solution.

A comprehensive case study helped us identify what worked well during the crisis and what was challenging. From the existing solutions and best practices we can better understand how the GaaP concept can be adapted to the Swiss context. Identified challenges serve as a motivation for the project which can be addressed by digital solution.

Figure 4: Interview Overview.

Ukrainian Refugee Crisis: Brief Overview

On February 24, 2022, Russia started a military invasion on the territory of neighboring Ukraine. This resulted in an unprecedented wave of refugees within Europe. Although refugee crises are not rare in recent European history (Syria, Afghanistan) and an influx of refugees is a constant situation in Europe, this time the migration was happening within the Europe itself and with an unprecedented speed. Even though the number of refugees is not as high compared to other refugee crisis this time people arrived much faster⁵ (Figure 5).

Europe has gained substantial experience during the Syria refugee crisis back in 2015 when a million refugees came to Europe over one year. But during the Ukrainian refugee crisis, it was much faster, when a million people arrived in 1 month. “And so they [public administration] couldn't use the best practice from the Syria crisis.” (Interview Org 2, 20:37).

Switzerland for the first time in recent history has received that many refugees. “What made 2022 unusual was the fact that an additional 74,959 people applied for protection status S. The total number of asylum and protection applications in 2022 was 99,470⁶. This corresponds to almost 1% of the permanent population of Switzerland [8]. Responding to this situation Switzerland has rashly approved new special migration status S. It allows for refugees to stay in the country, get social benefits as well as immediate right to work. In the first year it was granted to 95% of applicants. This situation resulted in the public administration being overwhelmed, and overall uncertainty due to emergence of the new processes.

Today, 4 years after the start of the war, most of the refugees with status S still reside in Switzerland. The situation for public administration is no longer that critical. As the main focus of the project is crisis response, our aim is to learn from the previous experience and build digital resilience of the society.

Figure 5: SEM Statistics on annual number of asylum applications ([link here](#)).

⁵ <https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/ukraine>

⁶ <https://archiv.migration.swiss/en/migration-report-2022/asylum-and-protection-status-s/a-few-figures>

“Refugee Journey”: Successes & Challenges

One of the main challenges of the current crisis was no clear understanding of refugees-related processes. Those processes differed significantly from canton to canton, from municipality to municipality, from one person to another. As one of the hosts shared with us, “it was kind of unclear who was responsible. Is the municipality responsible in any way? Is the canton responsible? Is the federal government responsible?” (Interview Host 01, 27:03). Thus, in the first stage of our case study, we have created a so-called refugee journey for the canton Zurich where we schematically describe activities and actors involved in the refugee crisis (Figure 6). Table 1 structures refugee activities in four stages: (1) Pre-arrival, (2) First weeks, (3) Settling and (4) Leaving. Stage 1 is out of the scope of the project, while Stages 2 to 4 are relevant for us. Most crisis related activities are situated in the Stage 2. Today refugees are mostly concerned with the activities of the Stages 3 and 4. The list of actors and activities is not exhaustive due to space limitation of the scheme.

 Refugee journey (Figure 6) demonstrates the diversity of actors and activities that can be potentially supported by the GaaP solution.

Figure 6: Refugee Journey.

#	1	2	3	4
Stage Name	Pre-arrival	First Weeks	Settling	Leaving
Duration	Varies	1-2 weeks – 1-2 months	Up to several years	Several weeks
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Finding information on the country ○ Making decision 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Temporary housing ○ Application for refugee status ○ Social welfare ○ Medical assistance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 'Permanent' housing ○ Integration plan (education, language courses, job search) ○ Social welfare ○ Medical insurance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Resign from the refugee status ○ Switch to regular migrant status ○ Refugee status expires
End Point	Arrival to the country	Receival of the refugee status	Settling	End of the refugee status

Table 1. Stages of the refugee journey

PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION: SUCCESSES & CHALLENGES

The public sector plays a special role in a refugee crisis. Under public sector, we primarily understand administrative agencies at the three levels of the Swiss federal system in this report. More specifically, the actors involved in the crisis are municipalities (Gemeinden), the cantonal administration (Social Welfare and Migration offices, Integration department, etc.) and the federal administration (SEM, BAZ). Additionally, in the case of the canton of Zurich service providing companies for refugee management (e.g., the AOZ, ORS) played crucial role in managing the crisis (Figure 6).

It is key to recognize that the “public sector” is not a homogenous body when it comes to refugee management. Tasks related to refugee management are distributed both across domains (e.g., security, integration or health) and across federal levels, performed by various agencies in concern.

Successes

In general, the public sector reacted rather quickly to the crisis and **demonstrated some organizational flexibility**. First, **status S** was launched in unprecedentedly short time. Public administration came up with a number of ad-hoc solutions for housing and humanitarian help to the displaced people. Another notable organizational measure is a creation of so-called **Anlaufstelle Ukraine-Hilfe**⁷. It was initiated by the cantonal social welfare office and allowed for a coordinated response and one-point of reference for the affected population.

Due to strong **federal principle of subsidiarity** in Switzerland, the municipalities could act rather independently and **solve the existing problems without getting approval “from above”**. On top of that, the **engagement of the public sector workers** helped to resolve many of the bureaucratic hurdles. As a municipality representative shared with us, *“at that moment we had no precise instructions and have then simply pursued our goals [to provide help to people in need]”* (Interview PA 13, 35:23).

“Although it was difficult times, our employees got very engaged in the situation. People were very flexible and innovative.” (Interview PA 7, 7:08).

Finally, to our surprise, many public sector organizations mentioned that the experience gained during the **Corona crisis was very helpful** in the refugee crisis despite a big difference in the nature of the crisis.

On a technical level, crisis response was not that active but still some initiatives were present. Many public sector organizations came up with the creation of the **“Ukraine-Hilfe” webpages** where information on the ongoing crisis was collected. Such one-pager solutions with all crisis-relevant information were available on almost all websites of the actors involved (federal offices, cantonal level, municipalities, etc.). Also, several organizations provided **translations** of the information into the language of the affected group (Ukrainian and English). This was highly appreciated by the displaced people as well as volunteers and social workers. **Hotline** at AOZ for refugees was also very helpful. Among **newly developed digital solutions** were the application RegisterMe⁸, developed by the Federal migration office to ease the registration process for refugees from Ukraine. More local initiatives include a development of **interfaces** for easier internal application processing as told to us by a representative of service provider company (Interview PA 11).

Challenges

Even though we have observed many positive experiences during the crisis there were also multiple challenges along the way. Two main challenges with which public sector had to deal were **uncertainty** created by the issuance of the new status S and the unprecedentedly **increased number of requests**. Moreover, the **processes differed significantly** for refugees from the Ukraine compared to other asylum-seekers in Switzerland. BAZ was

⁷ <https://www.zh-sozialkonferenz.ch/ukraine-hilfe/>

⁸ <https://registerme.admin.ch/>

no longer the first and only point of contact for refugees as it normally is. That created much of uncertainty for public sector as well.

All those factors led to **the system being overwhelmed** and incapable of providing the required services timely. As a representative of a service provider company shared with us, *“before the war [we have received] about 30 to 40 people a month. On April 30 [2022] we admitted 900 people. But the way of the admission was about the same”* (Interview PA 11, 16:34). Manual processes proved to be **unscalable** and inflexible in a crisis. Moreover, due to the federal structure of the Swiss public sector **many processes were not end-to-end** with unclear organizational boundaries, and there was not one person or organization that had an overview of the procedures related to Ukrainian refugees. As the consequence, while in normal life the system could cope with the refugee management, once being overwhelmed it could no longer function properly.

Additionally, information sharing on crisis was suboptimal. One of the recurring difficulties was related to **the information distribution and communication between different public sector organizations**. Representatives of municipalities who were responsible for the implementation of the cantonal policies were quite often incapable to reach out to the canton to get up-to-date information. As one municipality shared with us: *“Canton was completely overwhelmed. [In the beginning], we could not get through to the canton at all. And at a point when we received some information newsletters, we often would no longer need it”* (Interview PA 13, 46:13). At the same time, proper crisis communication is one of the crucial measures for the efficient crisis response.

Technically, many things were not in place and that caused much of the confusion [9]. **Data exchange** between organizations within public sector was often **suboptimal** during the crisis period. As there is **no holistic approach for the digital systems** in the canton of Zurich, there are almost no shared databases or well-established interfaces to exchange information. *“ICT system of different cantonal departments are incompatible with each other”* (Interview PA 7, 6:50). This results in many **data being transferred via emails, excel sheets, phone calls, etc.** Thus, the data exchange between organizations is unsystematic, difficult to trace, slow and in some cases error-prone. *“So today we have namely 130 persons who should be assigned to [our organization] according to the [canton], but we don't have track of them. And nobody knows who is taking care of these people.”* (Interview PA 11, 24:18).

At the same time, it is not only the question of technology but rather an organizational question. *“Not even one office of the canton [. . .] can share personal information with another office of the canton internally”* (Interview PA 1, 49:48). There are many restrictions on what data could be potentially shared with whom. As the result, many processes are manual and not scalable and public administration workers get overwhelmed with tasks. On a positive side, it is both *“the biggest challenge and also the situation with the biggest potential for improvement”* (Interview PA 11, 16:34).

NGO & PRIVATE BUSINESS: SUCCESSES & CHALLENGES

Enabling collaboration between actors of private and public sector is one of the key motivations for the current project. In crisis situations collaboration with NGOs and private companies is crucial, and effective collaboration can help to overcome difficulties quicker and easier. In some cases, NGOs and private business can even overtake certain responsibilities of the public administration. Recent crisis was no exception. NGOs and private organizations that previously worked with the topics of migrants, displaced people, refugees, social help, etc. became one of the key actors during the crisis (Red Cross, Caritas, SFH, etc.). Many of them collaborated with the public sector for the issues of accommodation, social help, integration, volunteering coordination, etc. Another noticeable example is an online matching platform for hosts and refugees which was developed by a civic and social organization Campax. Their solution was widely used during the crisis. On top of that, many other organizations were helping during the crisis, such as SBB, mobile providers, language schools, hotels, supermarkets, etc.

The collaboration between NGOs and public sector is crucial in crisis. During the Ukrainian refugee crisis, NGOs and private companies have overtaken some key activities in the refugee journey such as accommodation, dissemination, integration, volunteering coordination, etc.

Successes

Engagement of the civil society was equally very high during this crisis and numerous organizations were actively involved at various stages of the refugee journey. **Entrepreneurial mindset**, which is characteristic for private organizations and is often restricted for public sector, helped to come up with innovative solutions. Mobile operators provided free of charge SIM cards, hotels provided rooms for refugees, supermarkets helped with food, etc. Many NGOs were able to quickly react in the crisis and came up with many handy solutions. Among those were the translation of the website into Ukrainian and English, **coordination of the volunteers**, **collection of humanitarian help**, **integration and language courses**, **information sharing**, etc. This was extremely helpful for refugees and public sector alike.

On the technical level, the response of NGOs and private sector was much more active compared to those of the public sector. Similar to public administration, many organizations involved in crisis created their own **webpages** with the key information on the crisis which were often **translated** into Ukrainian or English.

Several solutions were developed specifically for the ongoing crisis and were widely used. In response to an unprecedented “host family” movement Campax had developed a **host-refugee matching platform** [10] for Switzerland within several weeks after the war started. Later, their solution was offered for the offices of public administration (BAZ, cantons and other NGOs). Collaboration was not always flawless but that is a good example of a collaboration between public and private sector.

Red Cross has addressed the problem of poor information sharing by developing an **information platform “Helpful”** specifically for the ongoing crisis. There, the information for all Ukrainian refugee related topics was very well-structured and had geo-specific recommendations on administration procedures or regional activities. Later, a telegram-chat was added also with well-structured information and the option to get answers in Russian and Ukrainian. This **telegram chat** was run by volunteers.

Challenges

Along many positive experiences NGOs and private organizations have faced a number of challenges when collaborating with public sector. Those can potentially be addressed by the digital platform. One of the recurring issues was the question of **data sharing**, **data privacy** and secure ways of **communication** especially when dealing with sensitive data. For this reason, several cantons rejected **collaboration** with the host-refugee matching platform although nothing similar was available at that moment.

To be more specific, governmental organizations expected that all data should be stored physically in Switzerland but at the same time Campax was “forced to look for third-party providers overseas to store this data

reliably because there is no public service for community projects like ours [in Switzerland].” (Interview Org 2, 37:05). At the same time, not rarely this strict attitude towards data privacy turned out to be superficial. “This is like a mantra from governmental organizations: “Is the data in Switzerland?” And if not then you have a huge problem. On the other side, sending around Excel list with sensitive information is not a problem. [...] you can do whatever you want, but the servers need to be in Switzerland, otherwise you're screwed” (Interview Org 2, 52:21). The same issues were mentioned by a number of other interviewees including public administration.

Federalism also posed significant challenges for the private sector. *“For the first couple of weeks BAZ was responsible for matching refugees and hosts. But then federalism took over and 26 cantons were given the task to do this matching on their own. [...] And then we struggled to coordinate, and we had 2 or 3 people only coordinating” (Interview Org 2, 38:41).*

Complicated processes and no clear understanding of the situation as a whole led to the creation of a large number of information webpages. Their abundance sometimes had the opposite effect of **increased difficulty to find information.**

And finally, **differences in mindset** in the approach of public and private sector was challenging during the collaboration between them. Although for both parties it was evident that private sector can be on a more entrepreneurial side and *“for the authorities it's more important not to make any mistake” (Interview Org 2, 1:10:30)* but it looks like a collaboration could still be possible.

VOLUNTEERS: SUCCESSES & CHALLENGES

During the Ukraine refugee crisis individual people showed exceptional dedication and involvement through actions such as collecting and distributing food and clothing, offering accommodation and providing translation assistance. The effective and prompt handling of the refugee flows would not be possible without the support of volunteers in the Canton of Zurich, who have been helping during the entire Ukraine refugee crisis. **Hundreds of volunteers were available around the clock to help the refugees as well as the staff of the cantonal organization: at the train station, in the cantonal shelters, at the employee centers, and at multiple donation points and organizations where one could receive food and all necessary for the first time.** Therefore, it is difficult to overestimate the role of volunteers in the management of this crisis.

While the GaaP solution aims to support organizations and companies, it also aims to serve individuals, and thus, it is crucial to examine the experiences and difficulties faced by these user groups.

Successes

Volunteering culture is very common in Switzerland and that helped many people to get engaged during the crisis. That happened both from the **organized volunteering** (Red Cross, SFH, AOZ, etc.) as well as from **self-organized groups** (Zurich helps Ukraine, train station volunteers, etc.).

From the positive experience, the volunteers appreciated the **availability of official information in Ukrainian or Russian languages** as that assisted them when helping refugees. Frequently, they were also able to refer the refugees to the official websites, which were more likely to have up-to-date information. What was particularly important for them was the autonomy and the possibility to get involved on their own initiative, and to form networks of volunteers as well as exchange information about the situation and the available resources. **Social media and messengers** (such as Telegram, Facebook, WhatsApp, etc.) turned out to be extremely useful and were one of the main means for the coordination of self-organized volunteering (Interviews Vol 1, Vol 3).

While hosts would also have to search for information, they found that **official information and updates** about the crisis were readily available on official websites and in the media. This made it easier for hosts to get information and make the necessary arrangements. In addition, information was also **available in Ukrainian**, which helped overcome language barriers and ensure that all refugees were adequately informed.

Challenges

Overall, while volunteers in the canton of Zurich had positive experience and were able to support many refugees during this difficult time, there were many challenges that need to be addressed to ensure a more effective response to such crisis situations. Most of the problems are organizational by its nature. By providing better **access to process knowledge** and resources and constantly updating the information that volunteers and refugees equally need, canton of Zurich could help to make the arrival and the first steps in Switzerland, go more smoothly.

At certain moments there were **difficulties in the distribution of information** due to the fact of having too many sources. This made it difficult to provide refugees with the necessary and up-to-date information in a timely manner, especially when there was confusion about the status S procedure and necessary registration steps. Additionally, **slow working processes** in organizations were frustrating for both volunteers and refugees, causing unnecessary delays.

Particularly affected by the problems of **information asymmetry** were a special group of volunteers, namely those who offered their accommodation to the refugees (so-called hosts). They were the people with whom the refugees were most in contact in their daily lives and thus the first to whom the refugees turned in case of questions or problems. In contrast to the volunteers who supported the organizations and thus had close contact with the process and an overview of the process, hosts were often not as well informed and had to work

with the refugees to acquire the necessary knowledge. No wonder hosts also had both positive and negative experiences.

Hosts often took on an advisory role and were also required to provide information far beyond accommodation issues: health care, public transportation, etc. The organization and availability of medical assistance made this task easier for the hosts. With the knowledge of the health system among the hosts and the short-term measures in the system, it could be ensured that the refugees received the necessary medical care and assistance.

One of the biggest challenges for hosts was the **lack of accountability and support** from government organizations and social workers. At the beginning the process of matching with a family was poorly supported. Even for locals it was challenging to understand how it functioned. *“First, I went to Canton A and shared my info to welcome refugees. Then I went to canton B, and also shared my data. Then it was some NGO, and then another NGO”* (Interview PA 7, 38:27). Many hosts ended up finding people through social media or private network.

All in all, this led to hosts feeling overwhelmed and unsupported, especially when trying to navigate the complex administrative processes of refugee assistance. There was also a great level of chaos in organizational processes, and unclear processes made it **difficult for hosts to know what was expected** of them. As one host shared with us: *“It was kind of unclear who was responsible. Is the municipality responsible in any way? Is the canton responsible? Is the federal government responsible?”* (Interview Host 01, 47:08). Simple errors in data and the lack of necessary documents further complicated these challenges, as hosts often had to spend a great deal of time and energy trying to resolve administrative issues.

REFUGEES WITH STATUS S: SUCCESSES & CHALLENGES

The most affected group of individuals were the refugees from the Ukraine themselves. This group of population is significantly different from previous groups of refugees both demographically and formally. First, they are very mobile and **can freely circulate in Europe**. Some of them have family or friends living in Switzerland. Consequently, **new processes** emerged. Normally, refugee-related processes are very centralized and are managed through BAZ. This time authorities were uncertain how to treat people from Ukraine, whether they were tourists, refugees or passers-by.

Demographically relocated population consisted **mostly of women with children** who had to leave their partners in homeland [8]. At the same time this is a highly **educated group** of population with **above average tech skills**. Around 70 percent of Ukrainian refugees have university degrees. About half have a **good level of English** (self-declared), with German and French skills gradually improving over time. On top of that this group is **highly self-organized** and relatively well-integrated with around 25% working age population being employed.

Successes

Despite the fact, that the administrative processes were not completely clear and smooth, refugees mentioned that the **availability of official information**, documents, and websites with **translations** to Ukrainian and Russian made it easier for them to navigate the bureaucratic system. They particularly appreciated it when the employees of the offices or other organizations had official information at their disposal and could provide it to them. If this was not the case, extraordinary commitment in the distribution of information was taken over by the **volunteers**. The **support from local community groups**, and **social workers** played a role in facilitating the integration of refugees. These organizations provided not only practical help, such as food and essential supplies, but also contributed to a sense of belonging through community activities. Social workers and **organizations like the Red Cross** were also important. **Quick school enrolment process** was also appreciated by many refugees.

In parallel to administrative processes, the refugees also faced the integration hurdle. There, the refugees mentioned in a positive context the existing accessible job opportunities for refugees, as well as the possibility of keeping a **remote job in Ukraine**. In the case of local job search, they experienced support through **job coaching programs**. The offer of **German language courses** was also widely utilized by many of them.

The cultural integration of refugees was largely facilitated by the supportive and welcoming nature of **host families and local volunteers**. Interviewee R_19 experienced positive engagement through activities like football matches, helping foster a sense of community: *“They took us to watch games... signed him up also for football. Everyone is quite responsive.”* (interview R_19, 24:56). Also, R_15 and R_16 highlighted the role of **volunteers** in helping navigate cultural barriers, such as learning local customs and languages, and participating in communal activities, contributing to a smoother transition into Swiss society. The **hosts’** willingness to help with day-to-day activities was also a key factor in the cultural integration of refugees, as noted by R_16.

On the technical front, the efficient handling of registration and administrative processes greatly aided the integration of refugees into the Swiss systems. Many interviewees appreciated how local volunteers and host families provided guidance and assistance with navigating bureaucratic hurdles. For instance, R_14 shared that registration processes, including accessing migration and social services, were handled smoothly: *“And already via email we received all the invitations: to the migration service, to the social service, everything we needed.”* (interview R_14, 06:29). Together with that, Ukrainian refugees proved themselves **as a well-organized community**. Through such digital platforms as Telegram, WhatsApp, Facebook, etc. they could quickly and efficiently share information, support each other and help in difficult situations. Around **50 open Telegram channels** were created and maintained during the crisis, most of which are still active today.

Challenges

Along positive experiences refugees have encountered many recurring challenges. **The federal system in Switzerland** posed various challenges for refugees, as administrative processes often differed from one municipality or canton to another. The lack of understanding of processes in different organizations, coupled with the need to **register multiple times** at several organizations, was often frustrating for refugees. **Long waiting time** and the **amount of duplicated paperwork** added to the existing stress. Further, it was **not always clear which of the information was up-to-date** and trustworthy. Since the regulations changed several times and not all organizations kept the information up to date, this resulted in a lot of **rumors and misinformation**. This created additional uncertainty for people unfamiliar with the system.

Delays and **confusion in payments and registration** was another big challenge. For example, R_17 experienced a three-week delay in receiving her first payment due to confusion over jurisdiction: *“Because of this Kloten-Zurich thing, they couldn’t decide where we belonged... the payments were delayed for about 3 weeks.”* (interview R_17, 41:13). Additionally, many refugees faced difficulty **navigating Swiss bureaucratic systems**, dealing with excessive paperwork and repetitive forms. R_19 noted inefficiencies, saying: *“With every little piece of information, they send you a letter... that could be sent by email.”* (interview R_19, 25:44). The waiting time for essential services, such as language courses and social payments, was also a recurring issue, with some refugees missing out on opportunities due to these delays. R_20 experienced delays in receiving her first payout: *“I received the payouts at the end of the month... that was not immediately.”* (R_20, 04:49).

At the same time **finding a job was challenging** due to the uncertainty created by their S status and the **diploma recognition**. Despite the desire to work, many refugees struggled to find employment due to the **language barrier** and **lack of proactive support** from employment centers, as R_19 highlighted: *“All he did was show me which sites to look at for work.”* (R19, 30:05). Thus, some refugees felt **unsupported in finding employment**, with job centers only providing minimal guidance on where to search for jobs without offering more direct assistance.

The refugees also encountered several technical and economic challenges, particularly in **understanding the social assistance system** and dealing with **housing shortages**. R_14 expressed confusion over how **social payments were calculated**, especially when earnings impacted the assistance received: *“I do not understand anything at all... I will be paid 150 francs as an incentive.”* (interview R_14, 12:02). Similarly, R_17 faced confusion over **insurance coverage**, which led to the cancellation of medical appointments: *“Sorry, your insurance does not cover it... your visit is canceled.”* (interview R_17, 25:21). In terms of housing, many refugees experienced difficulties securing stable accommodations. R_16 recounted the discomfort of living in cramped quarters with her family, where they had little personal space: *“The room has two bunk beds... ‘What is this?’ The room is two by three meters.”* (interview R_16, 23:15).

Having to work under high stress during the period in some cases created undesirable interpersonal dynamics between social workers and refugees. For example, refugees mentioned **unfriendliness in some organizations**. Combined with ignorance, this also makes it difficult for refugees to navigate the system. **Cultural and language barriers** were prevalent among refugees, making it challenging to integrate into Swiss society and access necessary services. R_14 and R_16 both struggled with the language gap, hindering their ability to communicate with locals and officials effectively: *“As for locals I do not (communicate with them) because the gap in the language is big... they speak fast.”* (interview R_14, 30:23). Additionally, cultural differences posed difficulties for some refugees, particularly in terms of adjusting to Swiss norms regarding food, daily life, and child-caring practices. The lack of social connections exacerbated these issues, with many refugees feeling isolated and relying on interactions with other Ukrainians to maintain a social life. R_19, for instance, found her social interactions limited due to the language barrier: *“I live in a village... I don’t see young people at all.”* (R_19, 19:42).

Overall, while refugees in Switzerland have access to some positive resources and supports, there are still many challenges that need to be addressed to ensure a smoother transition into their new lives.

Orchestration of the actors

Challenges public sector actors encountered differed both by domain and by federal level. However, across all evaluative interviews we conducted as part of the project, a core set of three challenges were almost always present. First, we have observed that many refugee-related **processes are not end-to-end** and often processes stop at the organizational boundaries and are not coordinated. Second, there is often **no interoperability between different organizations within public sector** such that digital systems of different organizations are not compatible with each other even in cases when they work closely together. And finally, in many cases it was **difficult to establish collaboration between heterogenous actors** which didn't allow for fast reaction and flexibility while preserving safety, legitimacy and fairness.

Based on the identified challenges we formulated the following capabilities that organizations need to have while managing the crisis.

Figure 7: Crisis Capabilities.

Government as a Platform Concept

Government as a Platform (GaaP) is a promising modern approach to the digital transformation of the public sector. Today when human-centric digital transformation in the public sector is part of the strategic goals of governments [11], GaaP becomes of high priority for policy-makers and governmental institutions. This is also reflected in a growing number of countries that apply the approach to their public service provision, e.g., Italy [12], the UK [13], Norway, and Estonia. While there is a growing body of research about GaaP as an innovative approach to digitalization in the public sector [14], [12], [15], [16], none of the studies so far has addressed the question of how GaaP and platformization might help in crisis situations.

In this section we explain the terminology of GaaP, its key principles and showcase GaaP implementations in other countries with special focus on Estonia.

Figure 8: Digital Platform Architecture.

Figure 9: GaaP Architecture.

Government as a Platform Glossary

Before we proceed to the elaboration on the principles of GaaP and its potentials for Swiss public administration let us first establish terminology which will be used throughout the project.

GaaP phenomenon is based on two pillars – a *digital platform* and an *eGovernment*. The term “*platform*” initially referred to systems within the private sector such as Uber or App Store, characterized by a “*stable core and flexible periphery*” [17]. The concept subsequently evolved to encompass “*digital platforms for development*”, exploring how such platforms can facilitate the creation of public value [18].

Technically, GaaP inherits the architecture of a *digital platform* therefore the key terms will be introduced on an example of App Store⁹ (Figure 8). Kuhn, Zavolokina, et al. [19] developed a framework to apply GaaP approach within public sector, and identified four dimensions that are important while moving toward GaaP: actors, architecture, activities and principles.

- *Actors*. There are three key roles: (1) *the platform owner*, who is responsible for the platform's development, maintenance, and governance; (2) *complementors*, those who develop and provide services using the tools offered by the platform owner; and (3) *users*, the individuals who consume these services [20].

⁹ <https://www.apple.com/app-store/>

- *Architecture*. From an architectural perspective, platforms can be deconstructed into three components: the central core, boundary resources, and the surrounding ecosystem [21]. (4) *The core's* defining characteristic is its centrality, encompassing both technical and organizational aspects. (5) *Boundary resources* act as a mediating layer, providing tools and rules that enable orchestration and facilitation. These resources are characterized by their flexibility and the level of control maintained by the platform owner. Finally, the main characteristic of an (6) *ecosystem* is its openness.
- *Activities*. This dimension describes main activities of the platform owner such that facilitation, orchestration, provision of tools, and management of assets.
- *Principles*. Main GaaP principles emphasize the importance of users' and complementors' engagement, they include *openness, participation* and *co-creation*.

Main difference of GaaP and a classical digital platform is that the user group should be *citizens, private* and *public organizations* (Figure 9). Platform owner should be *a governmental structure*. And a platform core as well as ecosystem should predominantly consist of *services for citizens*.

GaaP Best Practices. Estonian Case Study.

GaaP concept describes general principles while the concrete implementation differs significantly from country to country. Trade-offs between centralization and decentralization, openness and control, flexibility and standardization within platform architectures. In refugee contexts, for instance, enhanced openness may improve access to services but simultaneously increase vulnerability to exploitation [22]. Conversely, centralization offers greater oversight but could lead to exclusion of complementors [20]. Highly flexible platform tools necessitate well-defined governance structures to maintain safety [21].

Estonia is one of the leaders in application of GaaP approach. There, a digital government became the core of public administration starting 1991, thus being one of the oldest digital governments worldwide. Moreover, being a neighboring country with Ukraine it got one of the biggest flow of refugees. Thus, their experience is highly relevant for our study. Estonian case study is now being prepared and will be published separately.

Potentials of GaaP for Crisis

In this section we will apply GaaP concepts and describe (1) the situation *before the crisis* and (2-3) *during the crisis* using before mentioned GaaP terminology, and (4) *possible solutions* using GaaP principles (Table 2). As we saw, in normal-life scenario Swiss government could provide all the necessary services to the citizens without complications (1), i.e. connections between organizations worked well and services were provided. But when the crisis broke out (2), it appeared that existing processes (many of which are manual) were *not scalable* and public sector was overwhelmed. Fortunately, private sector, NGOs and individuals engaged themselves to help with addressing the crisis (3). In GaaP language it means that the *ecosystem* was already established. However, this help was limited due to the problems described in the section “*Refugee Journey*”: *Successes & Challenges*.

GaaP language helps us to reformulate this situation in the following way: *complementors* are present in a form of public and private sector, and *user group* is represented by refugees. But *boundary resources* (tools and rules) and *platform owner* are not established yet. Thus, in order for this system to function well, we need to *find an owner* and to *provide boundary resources* for the GaaP solution to work in crisis.

If we compare this to App Store example the situation is following. Before the crisis broke out Apple could develop all the applications by itself. Once the crisis happened different developers started to develop applications themselves, and it didn't work well both for users and developers. Developers couldn't reach their user group while users didn't know where to find application and which can they trust. In this situation it would be beneficial for all the involved parties if Apple designed a platform so that developers could faster develop safe application using the tools and rules, and users could access, and trust published applications.

Table 2. GaaP and the refugee crisis.

Platform Prototype

The platform prototype developed by our research team is designed to support better service delivery and coordination among refugees, organizations, and government agencies during crises. To provide a clearer understanding of its impact, we have created two short videos showcasing user stories and usage scenarios— one from the perspective of refugees ([link to the video](#)) and another highlighting organizations’ use of the platform ([link to the video](#)). The prototype reflects the concept of GaaP as a “platform of platforms” (see .

Figure 10), connecting various stakeholders through a shared digital infrastructure.

Figure 10 Tree Structure GaaP as a platform of platforms

Relation with the Bigger Ecosystem

The prototype is part of the broader GaaP ecosystem, which aims to enable collaboration across different actors. It has been designed to function flexibly in two ways:

- As a Standalone Platform: The prototype can operate independently to address specific needs, such as connecting refugees with host families or providing secure digital identities.
- Within a Larger GaaP Solution: The platform can also utilize and (re)use functionalities from a bigger system, such as eID for secure identity verification or payment solutions for financial transactions.

This approach helps cover most aspects of crisis management and ensures smoother interactions between stakeholders.

Figure 11: Crizzy high-level architecture.

First Iteration

The prototype (as in Figure 12) includes a range of features tailored to meet the needs of different user groups:

Figure 12. Landing Page Screenshot of Prototype

- For Refugees:
 - **SSI (Self-Sovereign Identity):** Enables refugees to manage their identity securely and independently. (See Chapter *Platform Applications*)
 - **RefuGPT:** A chatbot designed to assist refugees with everyday questions and navigating services. (See Chapter *Platform Applications*)
 - **Host-Family Matching platform:** Facilitates connections between refugees and host families, creating opportunities for secure and supportive living arrangements.
- For organizations:
 - **Service Registration:** Allows organizations to register services they offer, improving accessibility and coordination during crises.
 - **R2G (Refugee to Government):** A data-driven intelligence tool to help organizations better understand and respond to refugee needs, utilizing aggregated insights for effective decision making. (See Chapter *Platform Applications*)

Beyond these features, our prototype also includes functions related to education, employment, and volunteering, etc. These features provide a comprehensive foundation for addressing key challenges in refugee support and service coordination. By focusing on specific user needs, the prototype enhances usability and impact for both refugee and organizations. We completed the first round of user testing with 20 refugees. This testing provided feedback on usability, ethical considerations, and the overall user experience. Based on the qualitative data analysis [23], we deduced 4 design principles and created a functional prototype in our second iteration.

Second Iteration

The user categorization is further detailed for granular users needs management. An Admin role is also added to simulate the approval process of a request/registration.

For general public (no login required):

The public-facing section requires no login and offers two landing page views: Individual and Organization. The Individual view features the latest news, refugee arrival statistics, volunteer listings, and a full FAQ covering travel, registration, medical care, housing, work permits, and protection status S, while the Organization view provides a key refugee metrics dashboard alongside partner updates.

Beyond the landing page, visitors can access a Crisis Best Practices page with COVID-19 lessons learned, crisis response frameworks, and implementation guidelines; an About page covering the platform's mission, service overview, and contact information; and a Detailed Info page with a situation overview, monthly arrival data, a partner directory, and key contacts. Crizzy AI Chat is also available to everyone, even without an account.

For individuals (Refugees & Volunteers):

Both refugees and volunteers have their own dedicated features once logged in. Refugees can fill out a Housing Profile capturing details such as family size, location preference, language, urgency level, special needs, and pet details, then track their housing match status through the dashboard as it moves from submitted to under review to matched. They can also browse approved services across categories including housing, medical, food, transport, and legal, and submit service requests that go through admin review. Additionally, refugees can upload an identity document for verification and access both Crizzy AI Chat and an Information Resources page covering Swiss S-permits, healthcare, schools, and jobs. Volunteers, meanwhile, can register as a host by completing an accommodation profile with details such as type, capacity, number of bedrooms, pet rules, languages spoken, and availability. From their dashboard they can view pending requests and browse and respond to services on the services page — as well as upload an identity document for verification.

Volunteers can register as a host by completing an accommodation profile. From their dashboard they can view pending requests and browse and respond to services on the services page, and like refugees, they can also upload an identity document for verification.

For those with technical skills, a Developer Portal is also available to all individuals, providing the necessary digital toolkits to contribute to the platform, whether by offering services, sharing information, or creating digital artifacts.

Figure 13: Crizzy functional prototype.

For Organizations:

Organizations have a dedicated dashboard that flags any pending admin verification. Through Service Management, they can create service offers and requests, including software submissions with repo URL, deployment URL, tech stack, and installation guide, and manage incoming requests from refugees. Each organization maintains a full profile with a mission statement, website and social media links, areas of focus, available resources, services offered, partnership interests, and an Open to Networking toggle that controls visibility to other organizations. They can also browse other organization profiles to find and connect with like-minded partners, and create and manage housing matches between refugees and volunteers, including viewing match details and communicating with matched parties.

For Public Administrators:

Admins have full platform oversight, handling organization approvals and moderating all service submissions: including technical review of software services via repo URLs, demo links, and installation guides, regardless of their status. They can view all refugee and volunteer profiles, create and manage housing matches with status updates, and access secure messaging between matched parties.

Addressing Challenges

By embedding these above applications and features, our prototype directly addresses challenges observed during the Ukrainian refugee crisis (as described in Chapter [Case Study: Ukrainian Refugee Crisis in the Canton of Zurich](#)). Through a unified platform approach, it aims to enhance coordination, streamline processes, and improve information flow among diverse actors. Key benefits of the prototype include:

- **A Single Point of Entry:** The platform consolidates access to services and resources, reducing the need for refugees and stakeholders to navigate fragmented systems across federal, cantonal, and municipal levels. This addresses the issues of unclear responsibilities and redundant processes, improving overall efficiency.
- **Support for Organizations:** For public administrations and NGOs, our prototype offers tools like service registration and R2G to streamline the provision of services and gain actionable insights from data. This mitigates issues such as information silos, inefficient data sharing, and the overwhelming administrative burden observed during the crisis.
- **Autonomy and Transparency for Refugees:** Features like SSI empower refugees to manage their identity securely, while tools like RefuGPT and Host-Family Matching provide them with tailored assistance, fostering autonomy and improving integration outcomes. These features address challenges related to misinformation, lack of clarity, and language barriers.
- **Integration with the Larger Ecosystem:** The prototype can function as a standalone solution or integrate with existing systems by embedding links and files from other authorities, such as eID and financial assistance, ensuring adaptability and scalability. This feature is beneficial for tackling the fragmented digital infrastructure and promoting a cohesive response in crisis situation.
- **Ethical and Inclusive Design:** By embedding information about data usage, the prototype ensures responsible data management and emphasize human autonomy. In addition, we keep the design clean and simple, with clear navigation and easy-to-understand icons. This address concerns around data privacy, fairness, and digital divide.

Platform Applications

One of the main GaaP components is the **application layer**. Here, end-users—whether citizens, businesses, or public administrations—can access the desired services. These applications are developed either by **complementors** or the **platform owner**. The level of platform openness determines how easily new applications can be integrated into the platform and the extent to which their development and deployment are regulated by the platform owner. Below are the applications designed by our research team.

SSI for refugees

The Ukrainian refugee crisis revealed challenges for both refugees and organizations in the Swiss asylum process. While refugees are faced with time-consuming and cumbersome administrative tasks, involved authorities and organizations are overwhelmed with slow paper-based processes, redundant work, and wrong data. We propose a digital identity (eID) to mitigate these issues. The challenges of implementing a centralized identity, particularly given Switzerland's decentralization, led us to choose a Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) concept. Following a design science research approach, we iteratively developed a prototype and evaluated it with refugees and different organizations. Based on the analysis of collected feedback, we formulated design principles for SSI-based eID for refugees and described how these principles impact feasibility, refugees' empowerment, and organizations' efficiency. We formulated the main principles for refugee empowerment through three lenses: SSI-comprehensive, early-access digital wallet; eID-gradual increase in identification; and GaaP-open identity platform [24].

Figure 14: SSI + Desk.

Figure 15: SSI + Wallet.

Data-Driven Intelligence in Crisis

This section presents applications developed by Kilian Sprenkamp within the scope of his PhD thesis work.

R2G (Refugees to Government)

Refugees to Government (R2G) is a data-driven application designed to enhance refugee management by public sector professionals [25]. The application utilizes community data from open Telegram groups to gather real-time information about refugee needs, offering a bottom-up approach to understanding and addressing these needs. It employs advanced natural language processing techniques, such as BERTopic for topic modeling and GPT-4 for chatbot functionality, to analyze multilingual data and provide timely insights. R2G allows users to visualize refugee needs across different geographical locations and time periods, and its chatbot feature enables interactive querying of the dataset to obtain detailed and personalized information. This tool supports decision-making by providing public sector professionals with dynamic, accurate, and relevant data to better tailor services and policies to the refugee community.

Figure 16: R2G interface.

RefuGPT

RefuGPT is a bi-layered, LLM-based chatbot specifically designed to assist Ukrainian refugees in Switzerland with their information-seeking needs. Developed using a Design Science Research Methodology, RefuGPT integrates both official and community-based information to provide reliable, timely, and comprehensive answers to users' inquiries about government processes and essential services. The chatbot operates on the Telegram platform, offering a familiar and accessible interface that supports multiple languages, including Ukrainian and Russian. By employing retrieval augmented generation and a context-aware LLM, RefuGPT effectively addresses common refugee challenges, such as fragmented information, misinformation, lack of interaction, and language barriers. Through its bi-layered approach, RefuGPT enhances the information-asking experience by consolidating diverse information sources into a single, interactive tool, thereby alleviating disorientation among refugees and streamlining their integration process.

Figure 17: RefuGPT interface

Hackathon on Crisis Apps (2025, UZH)

In late 2025, we organized a dedicated hackathon to **test and evaluate digital crisis response solutions**. This event served as a critical testing ground for our prototype GaaP solution, specifically designed for the Swiss context. To achieve this, we invited three organizations involved in the refugee crisis in Switzerland—the [Asylum Organization Zurich \(AOZ\)](#), [UNHCR](#) and [SEET](#)—to share real-world challenges their organizations face. Participants were **27 computer science students** who formed 9 teams to develop innovative prototypes. To support them, our practice partner [Ergon Informatik AG](#) joined the hackathon to provide technical expertise and guidance.

Video documentation: https://youtu.be/OmYUpurGOYM?si=hq2qAKt0k_oyunrn

Figure 18: Hackathon on Crisis Apps.

Hackathon Overview

The hackathon was designed as a part of the university seminar "Digital Platforms for Resilience in Crisis". This structure allowed us as organizers to adequately prepare students for the upcoming challenges through four preparatory lectures. These sessions covered essential theoretical foundations, including GaaP principles, crisis informatics, and Design Thinking methodology.

The hackathon lasted for 48 hours spread over 3 days. The event was enriched by insights from external experts. Oleg Lavrovsky delivered a keynote on the impact of hackathons for crisis response, and Michael Schröder (Ergon AG) provided input on *Impact mapping* technique. Throughout the 48-hour event, students were supported by mentors from our research team and professional developers from Ergon, ensuring that the prototypes were both technically sound and contextually relevant.

Challenges

Students were proposed three challenges from our partner organizations, each addressing a problem they were experiencing during the Ukrainian refugee crisis or technical bottleneck identified in our case study:

- **Virtual Legal Assistance Rights Mapping [UNHCR]:** How might we determine the legal status of a refugee for pro bono lawyers, so that their advice can be given more quickly and accurately?
- **Coordination of emergency supplies [AOZ]:** How might we coordinate the purchasing and storage of emergency supplies for AOZ employees so that they can quickly provide housing and essentials during unpredictable migration crises?
- **Mentor-Mentee Matching Platform [SEET]:** How might we help SEET admin to match mentors and mentees more efficiently so that SEET program can be more scalable?

// Hackathon as a seminar – Course Structure

Goal

Prototype a crisis response application for the GaaP platform

Participants

20 – 30 computer science students, forming 7-10 groups

Possible Challenges

- Information sharing during crisis
- Data analytics for crisis
- Matching platforms

Figure 19: Seminar Structure "Digital Platforms for Resilience in Crisis".

Outcomes

During the intensive 48-hour event, student teams successfully developed 9 innovative digital prototypes addressing three crisis challenges. These solutions ranged from LLM-driven retrieval augmented generation chatbots designed to assist pro-bono lawyers, to centralized resource allocation trackers and mentor-mentee matching platforms.

In their follow-up reports, students mapped out how these decentralized prototypes could seamlessly interact with and profit from the central GaaP core. They demonstrated that by connecting complementors to shared boundary resources (such as secure eID verifications and data standards), crisis applications can be co-created rapidly. Ultimately, the outcomes validated that a GaaP infrastructure significantly enhances societal digital resilience through modular, reusable components and compounding network effects.

SEET Mentoring
Connecting Minds, Building Futures

Admin Dashboard

Monitor Real Scoring (70% Algorithm + 15% Chat + 15% Feedback) & Final Match Decisions

7 Total Requests | 0 Both Continue | 0 Both End | 0 Mixed Decisions | 0 High Score (9-100%)

MATCH DETAILS	ALGORITHM SCORE	CHAT SCORE	FEEDBACK SCORE	USER DECISIONS	FINAL SCORE	ACTIONS
Alina Johnson → David Wilson ID: 1 09/15/2025	0.0%	0.0%	0.0% No change	2 Pending	0.0% REJECT	Approve Reject
Bob Smith → Maria Schneider ID: 3 09/15/2025	0.0%	0.0%	0.0% No change	2 Pending	0.0% REJECT	Approve Reject
Sophia Mueller → Daniel Meier ID: 5 09/15/2025	100.0%	0.0%	0.0% No change	2 Pending	7.0% REJECT	Approve Reject
Thomas Weber → Claire Lohrer ID: 4 09/15/2025	0.0%	0.0%	0.0% No change	2 Pending	0.0% REJECT	Approve Reject
Elena Rossi → Robert Lehmann ID: 1 09/15/2025	0.0%	0.0%	0.0% No change	2 Pending	0.0% REJECT	Approve Reject

Figure 20: Mentoring Platform, Team 2.

Figure 21: LLM-driven chatbots for legal assistance. Team 6.

Platform Governance: From Prototype to Institutional Capacity

Our project makes clear that useful digital components are not enough. For GaaP to become a durable crisis-response capacity, it needs an institutional arrangement that defines ownership, responsibilities, participation rights, accountability, and rules for data sharing. The Swiss federal system makes this both difficult and promising. Federalism and subsidiarity allowed municipalities and cantonal actors to react flexibly during the Ukrainian refugee crisis. Yet the same structure also produced fragmentation: processes differed across cantons and municipalities, responsibilities were sometimes unclear, and data exchange was often slow, informal, or impossible. The problem is not decentralization itself. The problem is decentralization without sufficient orchestration.

The project also reveals a governance vacuum. Public administrations are central to crisis response, but may lack a clear legal obligation, mandate, or resources to maintain a GaaP infrastructure. NGOs and private actors may have expertise and speed, but they cannot legitimately take over core public functions without legal basis, delegation, and accountability. As a result, actors work in parallel, solutions are duplicated, and the ecosystem’s potential remains underused.

Governance issue	What the project observed	Suggested GaaP response
No clear platform owner	Actors mobilized, but no one had system-wide responsibility	Define a mandated platform steward
Fragmented responsibilities	Processes stopped at organizational boundaries	Establish shared boundary resources
Weak interoperability	Data exchange relied on emails, Excel sheets, calls	Require minimum interoperability standards
NGO and private-sector role unclear	Civic actors helped, but lacked formal integration	Create certified participation and delegation models
Federalism cuts both ways	Local autonomy helped, but coordination suffered	Coordinate the core, decentralize services

Legal Findings

GaaP

GaaP is described as an approach to public administration aimed at creating a modular, interoperable digital platform that does not itself perform administrative tasks, but rather “orchestrates” the interaction between state and non-state actors in the course of performing those tasks [19]. GaaP remains a concept not enshrined in legislation and therefore lacks legal binding force for public administration (PA) bodies to participate in it or to further develop it as a part of constitutional and administrative law doctrine GaaP [26].¹⁰ This issue does not allow one to determine with sufficient certainty who must ensure interoperability and participation in GaaP. However, the e-ID [24]¹¹, as one of GaaP’s core components, demonstrates that it is possible to require all levels

¹⁰ Within Swiss federalism, the principle of subsidiarity (Art. 5a para. 2 Federal Constitution of the Swiss Confederation (Cst.) of 18 April 1999, SR 101) mandates that decision-making remain at the lowest possible level. Consequently, if a matter can be resolved by a natural person on their own, there is no need for intervention by the authority. Including DigiV (esp. Arts. 3 and 11) and EMBAG in their current configuration. Bundesgesetz über den elektronischen Identitätsnachweis und andere elektronische Nachweise (E-ID-Gesetz, BGEID), vom 20. Dezember 2024. Verordnung vom 2. April 2025 über die digitale Verwaltung und die Informatik (DigiV), SR 172.019.1. Bundesgesetz vom 17. März 2023 über den Einsatz elektronischer Mittel zur Erfüllung von Behördenaufgaben (EMBAG), SR 172.019.

¹¹ Art. 24 E-ID-Gesetz, BGEID.

of public administration to accept elements of such an architecture through law, although this may be a very lengthy and onerous process. GaaP can therefore move from concept to reality when responsibilities are clearly allocated by law, and when prior political commitment exists. The reverse order, trying to create such a platform before a legal framework, proved difficult.

Challenges: Governance Vacuum

The key issue is framed not as whether a GaaP is permissible in general within the current legal framework, but as how—through what legal mechanisms[27] —to ensure: (a) the allocation of rights, duties, and responsibility among levels of government and ecosystem participants; (b) the binding nature of baseline interoperability and participation; (c) a stable framework for connecting non-state actors while meeting compliance requirements (e.g. data protection and respect for human rights).

PA is reluctant to assume permanent responsibility for GaaP because no direct legal obligation requires them to do so. NGOs or volunteers, even if they have the resources and expertise, do not have the legal title to assume the PA's role “by default”, since (a) their participation is only possible within the limits of PA discretion and delegation and/or (b) is limited by their statutory objectives and/or volunteering governed by civil law. Although all relevant actors are capable of carrying out different tasks, they often act independently, which creates inefficiencies and duplicates both tasks and solutions (interviews with PA). For example, although AOZ is responsible for housing, some NGO may also assist, yet its independent role limits visibility and integration. However, where an NGO assumes core AOZ housing functions, e.g. by maintaining the official register of accommodated refugees, allocating accommodation to large numbers of them, and coordinating data exchange, the arrangement begins to resemble an unauthorized exercise of PA functions without a proper legal mandate [28].

This is how the contradiction and governance vacuum arise: The PA is not obliged to support nor institutionalize the GaaP core (and therefore avoids additional responsibility), and the NGO cannot legitimately “replace” the PA in the core of GaaP without a law/delegation and data. The importance of a clear legal basis and formal mandate is illustrated by Estonia, Ukraine, Russia, and numerous other jurisdictions, all of which have implemented GaaP, to varying degrees, through one or more laws or regulatory instruments [29].

Pathway

We acknowledge the existing challenges and that the organizational dimension may be one of the main obstacles to GaaP implementation. One possible solution could be to conceive GaaP as a sui generis legal construct with multi-level and polycentric governance (partly comparable to the holding logic or a quaNGO like AOZ). What matters is the existence of sufficient political commitment to establish an appropriate legal and organizational framework.

Why sui generis approach? Closed platforms (private), open platforms under state control, and community-based platforms managed by civil society [30] – none of these models fully meet GaaP requirements, as GaaP combines horizontal and vertical relationships between actors, operates within a strict legal and IT framework, and requires, among others, PA participation, the possibility of external contributions, i.e. management and curation in governance.

Proposed pathway forward to GaaP would first require clarification of (a) GaaP as a concept and its objectives; (b) GaaP as a possible legal form and its characteristics; (c) the distribution of rights and obligations between state and non-state actors; and (d) the institutional mechanisms needed to balance coordination and actor autonomy.

Possible practical-oriented steps could include identifying a suitable PA-based legal entity at the federal or cantonal level, concluding framework agreements with existing public entities, and structuring the participation of NGOs and private actors in a way that balances decentralization and coordination. Together, these steps could support both managerial and curatorial approaches to GaaP governance to reflect its sui generis legal nature.

Way Forward

The project suggests that a Swiss GaaP for crisis response should not be understood as a centralized super-platform replacing existing public, private, or civic initiatives. Rather, it should be conceived as a governance arrangement for coordinated decentralization. Its core task would be to define and maintain common boundary resources: interoperability standards, data-sharing rules, onboarding procedures for NGOs and private actors, accountability mechanisms, and reusable digital components. Such a platform would preserve the advantages of Swiss federalism while reducing the fragmentation that became visible during the Ukrainian refugee crisis. In this sense, the platform owner should not act as a monopolistic service provider, but as a steward of a shared crisis-response infrastructure.

The application of the GaaP principles seems to be promising although not an immediate approach for Switzerland. We see that Switzerland is putting significant efforts and resources into digitalization of public administration and thus Government as a Platform (GaaP) concept deserves consideration. Through the Ukrainian refugee crisis case study, we have identified that the use of ICT in crisis management—both during this event and the COVID-19 pandemic—has been underutilized, revealing significant potential for improvement.

This report has highlighted the key challenges faced by public administration, civil society, and refugees during the Ukrainian refugee crisis. Our findings show that significant potential for improvement remains untapped: too many processes are still performed manually, data exchange within and across public sector organizations is limited and, in some cases, error-prone. As a result, cross-organizational collaboration during crises is not always possible.

The GaaP concept was introduced and its potential for crisis response was demonstrated. We have shown that many components of a GaaP architecture are already present in the observed context, i.e. ecosystem actors, complementors, end-users. What is still missing is a designated platform owner and formally defined boundary resources (shared tools and rules). In the first iteration of our prototype, we demonstrated what such a platform could look like, and we presented several applications developed by our research team.

Based on the study findings, we offer the following recommendations to policymakers and public administrations. First, **designate a mandated platform owner**: without a clear institutional owner, coordination will continue to depend on individual initiative rather than durable structures. Second, **establish a legal basis before scaling technology**: the key challenge is organizational and legal, not technical, and experience in countries with existing GaaP such as Estonia shows that a formal mandate is a prerequisite for cross-level interoperability. Third, **introduce minimum interoperability standards for crisis data exchange**; such rules would help replace the emails and spreadsheets. Fourth, **create formal onboarding models for NGOs and private actors**, so that civil society can contribute effectively without operating outside its mandate. Fifth, **invest in shared digital components during peacetime** — eID, service registries, decision-support dashboards — so they are ready to scale when needed rather than improvised under pressure. Sixth, **leverage existing civic engagement** through structured channels, turning the strong volunteer response observed during the crisis into a sustainable part of crisis resilience. Finally, **treat cross-cantonal coordination as a design requirement from the outset**, not an afterthought — refugees and host families paid the cost of jurisdictional inconsistencies that better-designed infrastructure could prevent.

As the project concludes, the key research and development milestones have been completed. Several academic publications are currently in preparation or under review. Given the typical timelines of academic publishing, some of these project's contributions will appear over the coming years.

The groundwork has been laid. Whether Switzerland moves toward a resilient, platform-based crisis infrastructure depends on the decisions made now — before the next crisis arrives.

List of Acronyms

ADR	Action Design Research
AOZ	Asylum Organization Zurich
BAZ	Bundesasylzentrum (Eng.: Federal Asylum Centre)
DIZH	Digitalization Initiative of the Zurich Higher Education Institutions
DSR	Design Science Research
ETH	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich (Eng.: Federal Institute of Technology Zurich)
GaaP	Government as a Platform
ICT	Information and communications technology
LLM	Large Language Model
NGO	Non-governmental Organization
ORS	Organisation for Refugee Services (https://www.ors-service.org/schweiz)
RAC	Rapid Action Call
SEET	Support Education, Empower Together (https://seet.ch/)
SFH	Die Schweizerische Flüchtlingshilfe (Eng.: The Swiss Refugee Council)
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UZH	University of Zurich
ZHAW	Zurich University of Applied Sciences

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Appendix 1. List of Interviews.

Sphere of Activity	Interviews	Length	Interviewees
Public Administration (PA)	14		
IT department	1	1:12:45	PA 1
Integration Office	1	1:02:09	PA 2
Department of Justice	1	0:50:04	PA 3, PA 4
Veterinary office	1	0:42:25	PA 5
Education office	1	0:42:00	PA 6
Employee of the canton	1	0:53:56	PA 7
Social welfare office	1	1:00:53	PA 8, PA 9
Service provider company	2	2:55:26	PA 10, PA 11
Midsized municipality 1 (ZH)	1	0:35:33	PA 12
Midsized municipality 2 (ZH)	2	2:19:45	PA 13 - 15
Educational administration	2	1:26:43	PA 16, PA 17
NGOs & Private Organization (Org)	13		
Campaign organization that developed refugee-host matching platform	3	3:42:04	Org 1 – 3
Ukrainian refugee specific information platform developed by a humanitarian organization	2	2:48:52	Org 4 - 6
Refugee organization	1	1:00:17	Org 7
Humanitarian Organization (ZH)	1	0:41:00	Org 8
Swiss charity organization	1	0:42:09	Org 9
Housing cooperative	1	0:40:00	Org 10
Ukrainian-Swiss business Association	1	0:48:25	Org 11
Church in a midsized municipality (ZH)	1	0:40:25	Org 12
Self-organized group of volunteers	2	1:22:15	Org 13, Org 14
Individuals	28		
Refugees (R)	20	12:09:14	Ref 1- 20
Hosts (H)	4	2:27:5	Host 1 – 4
Volunteers (V)	4	3:13:45	Vol 1 – 4
TOTAL	55	43:57:10	59

Appendix 2. Project Publications.

All publications from the project are listed and updated in the [Zotero Library Collection](#).

2025

R. Tang, G. Miscione, Z. Katashinskaya, and L. Zavolokina, “Listening to Refugee Voices by foregrounding their Ethical Dilemmas in Digital Platform,” ICIS 2025 Proceedings. 6, Dec. 2025. https://aisel.aisnet.org/icis2025/is_good/is_good/6

This research explored ethical dilemmas faced by refugees when navigating humanitarian digital platforms during crises. Through interviews and prototype evaluations with Ukrainian refugees in Switzerland, we identify two fundamental ethical dilemmas: Data Privacy vs. Service Access for Survival and Convenience vs. Empowerment. Our findings reveal that refugees experience intensified ethical tensions when forced to choose between surrendering personal data and accessing vital services, or between algorithmic efficiency and personal agency. Based on these insights, we developed four design principles: Tiered Privacy Control, Participatory Algorithmic Governance, Human-in-the-Loop Verification, and Community Support Recognition. This study contributes to information systems literature by foregrounding vulnerable users' perspectives and providing actionable design principles to create more ethical and inclusive digital platforms for humanitarian response.

K. Sprenkamp, S. Eckhardt, L. Zavolokina, and G. Schwabe, “From Information-Seeking to Information-Asking: Designing RefuGPT, a Chatbot for Ukrainian Refugees in Switzerland,” Digit. Gov.: Res. Pract., vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 1–21, Dec. 2025, doi: [10.1145/3735140](https://doi.org/10.1145/3735140)

A key challenge for refugees is accessing relevant information about their host country. However, refugees often face disorientation during their information-seeking process. Disorientation is driven by language barriers, a digital divide, high urgency, and an evolving situation, which hinders the refugees' ability to access information. Addressing the issue of disorientation, we propose an IT artifact, i.e., a chatbot called RefuGPT, designed through a rigorous Design Science Research Methodology. RefuGPT leverages the power of a large language model (LLM), GPT-4 while accessing two distinct sources of information, i.e., official and community-based information utilizing retrieval augmented generation and prompt-based learning (Figure 1). We assess RefuGPT's usefulness and usability through an ex-post evaluation in a naturalistic setting with Ukrainian refugees. Hence, we show that our bi-layered LLM-based chatbot can effectively assist refugees. They thus move from information-seeking to a more effortless information-asking. Based on those insights, we propose design principles as well as practical recommendations for refugee chatbots.

Z. Katashinskaya, G. Miscione, and L. Zavolokina, “Mind the GaaP – Solution Traps in Crisis Response Applications,” in Academy of Management Proceedings, Jul. 2025, p. 11036. [doi:10.5465/AMPROC.2025.11036abstract](https://doi.org/10.5465/AMPROC.2025.11036abstract).

What is taken for granted becomes visible when it breaks. One of the common things that can be observed during crises is the so-called solution trap, i.e. a situation in which the coexistence of solutions with diverse origins hinders the achievement of the desired results. These become particularly evident when the urgency that any crisis generates reduces the chances of orchestrating the response adequately. We argue that the Government as a Platform approach can mitigate the inevitable solution traps in crises, thus allow for better resilience. Our research is empirically based on a two-year case study of the digital response of a variety of actors in a Switzerland to the Ukrainian refugee crisis. Based on existing literature and our direct research experience, we propose an extended definition of the solution trap notion during crisis by specifying its potential causes such as coexistence of competing or interfering partial solutions, accumulation of technical debt, missed potentials due to opportunity costs, unintended consequences, among others. We conclude by arguing that this cause may guide the mobilization of a Government as a Platform approach.

K. Sprenkamp, M. Dolata, G. Schwabe, and L. Zavolokina, “Data-driven intelligence in crisis: The case of Ukrainian refugee management,” *Government Information Quarterly*, vol. 42, no. 1, p. 101978, Mar. 2025, doi: [10.1016/j.giq.2024.101978](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2024.101978).

The ongoing conflict in Ukraine has triggered a humanitarian crisis, leading to a substantial increase in refugees. This situation presents a significant challenge for European countries, emphasizing the urgent need for effective refugee management strategies. Hence, effective decision-making is needed for the public sector to create a better livelihood for refugees. In this study, we propose using the concept of intelligence defined by Herbert Simon for effective refugee management. Following the Design Science Research Methodology, we utilize 58 semi-structured stakeholder interviews within Switzerland to identify problems and define design goals that facilitate intelligence in refugee management. Based on the design goals, we developed R2G – “Refugees to Government”, an application that utilizes community data and state-of-the-art NLP, including a chatbot interface, to offer an interactive dashboard for identifying refugee needs. The chatbot allows policymakers to interact with refugee data through dynamic, conversational queries, enabling real-time identification of refugee needs and providing data-driven intelligence. Our assessment of R2G, facilitated through 28 semi-structured interviews, resulted in four design principles for data-driven intelligence in refugee management: community-driven insight, spatial-temporal knowledge, multilingual data synthesis and visualization, and interactive data querying through chatbots. Additionally, we provide policy recommendations emphasizing the ethical use of community data, the integration of advanced NLP techniques in government processes, and the need for shifting governmental roles towards data analytics.

2024

A. Garazha, C. Merz, G. Schwabe, and L. Zavolokina, “Resilience in Times of Crisis: Empowering Refugees with Self-Sovereign Identity,” Dec. 2024. https://aisel.aisnet.org/icis2024/general_is/general_is/2

The Ukrainian refugee crisis, beginning in 2022, revealed challenges for both refugees and organizations in the Swiss asylum process. While refugees are faced with time-consuming and cumbersome administrative tasks, involved authorities and organizations are overwhelmed with slow paper-based processes, redundant work, and wrong data. We propose a digital identity (eID) to mitigate these issues. The challenges of implementing a centralized identity, particularly given Switzerland's decentralization, led us to choose a Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) concept. Following a design science research approach, we iteratively developed a prototype and evaluated it with refugees and different organizations. Based on the analysis of collected feedback, we formulated design principles for SSI-based eID for refugees and described how these principles impact feasibility, refugees' empowerment, and organizations' efficiency. We formulated the main principles for refugee empowerment through three lenses: SSI-comprehensive, early-access digital wallet; eID-gradual increase in identification; and GaaP-open identity platform.

2023

P. Kuhn, L. Zavolokina, D. Balta, and F. Matthes, “Toward Government as a Platform: An Analysis Method for Public Sector Infrastructure,” Sep. 2023. <https://aisel.aisnet.org/wi2023/41/>

Government as a Platform (GaaP) is a promising approach to the digital transformation of the public sector. In practice, GaaP is realized by platform-oriented infrastructures. However, despite successful examples, the transformation toward platform-oriented infrastructures remains challenging. A potential remedy is the analysis of existing public infrastructure regarding its platform orientation. Such an analysis can identify the gaps to an ideal platform-oriented infrastructure and, thus, support the transformation toward it. We follow the design science research methodology to develop a four-dimensional analysis method. We do so in three iterations, and, after each iteration, evaluate the method by its application to infrastructures in practice. With regard to theory, our results suggest extending GaaP conceptualizations with a specific emphasis on platform

principles. With regard to practice, we contribute an analysis method that creates proposals for the improvement of infrastructures and, thus, supports the transformation toward GaaP.

K. Sprenkamp, L. Zavolokina, M. Angst, and M. Dolata, “Data-Driven Governance in Crises: Topic Modelling for the Identification of Refugee Needs,” May 2023. doi: [10.1145/3598469.3598470](https://doi.org/10.1145/3598469.3598470)

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